
FOUNDATIONS OF EUTHANASIA: SOME MORAL PROBLEMS

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Abstract

Death is the end of life. Human life may end in various ways, sometimes he dies in an accident, dies naturally in old age, dies in disease etc., but in today's society some sort of deaths are most complicated issues in moral philosophy. Life is invaluable. Man loves his life, he wants to protect and prolong his life. Everyone has the right to make their own decisions. But there is controversy over the morality of his decision to end his life. In this paper I will discuss the relation between morality and euthanasia. In this way I will mention the meaning of suicide, assisted suicide and euthanasia. I will analysis euthanasia and its moral foundations, what ethical issues arise in the case of euthanasia and how ethical issues can be minimized, finally I will try to find out which situation is reasonable for Euthanasia.

Keywords: Euthanasia, Suicide, Assisted Suicide, Terminally Ill, Pain, Disease.

Introduction

Human life may end in various ways, sometimes he dies in an accident, dies naturally in old age, dies in disease etc., but in today's society some deaths are most complicated issues in moral philosophy, like suicide, euthanasia, assisted suicide etc. those are an important controversial moral issue, involves the intentional killing of a human life in our society. Assisted suicide and euthanasia have become a special and popular subject of moral philosophy and there has been a lot of writing on it. Especially after 1984, when the Dutch Supreme Court legalized euthanasia and auxiliary death in the Netherlands. The Netherlands was the first country in the West to legalize euthanasia and auxiliary death. In applied Ethics a big point of debate is the exact difference among euthanasia, assisted suicide and suicide. Even some words those are using for describing them, fail to show the clear difference among them. Generally, there is lot of confusion in the common people about the nature of euthanasia, assisted suicide and suicide. So, we need to describe the nature of these three and the real differences between them need to be made public. Controversy pervades contemporary debate over the decades of the moral status of euthanasia. It remains a highly controversial moral issue, with clinical, political, religious, legal, and ethical considerations playing an important role. We can realize the value of life with face of death. Euthanasia is one way of them by which human life ends. Death is always undesirable, but some of the cases people desire own death for getting relief from painful life in the case of euthanasia. Death is so final and unfortunate, but some deaths are better than unbearable painful life that is being suffered by patient with incurable disease. The patient who is suffering with enormous pain from incurable disease rarely die comfortably and he is dependent on others for life's basic needs and functions. After a dignified, meaningful life, many people are trapped in their isolated mind and body. Euthanasia is comfortable and sympathetic dignified death that relieves suffering and honor life. Now we will define the meaning of euthanasia.

Ethical issues on different ways of death

The reason is that we need to understand the difference between the nature of suicide and euthanasia. Though assisted suicide and euthanasia are very close by their nature. Suicide is surely very common among primitive peoples. But it has peculiar characteristic. According to the Oxford English Dictionary, the word 'suicide' comes from the Latin word 'suicidium', which means 'to kill oneself', first used in 1651. Although Alfred Alvarez, has discovered the usage of the word from 1635. Definition of suicide have been given by different thinkers in different ways. Some have said that suicide is a way of killing by oneself and some have said that it is an act where the killer himself dies directly or indirectly by his positive or negative actions. Though there are many definitions of 'suicide', In the case of giving a common definition, we can say that if a person intentionally ends his life in a situation where no one else has forced him to do it and in a situation where the situation does not seem worthy of survival, his death can be called suicide. From historical usage Craig Paterson mention the definition of suicide is 'one who dies by his own hand; one who commits self-murder.'¹ And later in its use we see that the word 'suicide' is used to connote the wrongful killing of oneself, for example, 'self-murder' and 'self-slaughter'.

Durkheim said that in the nineteenth century, the tendency to commit suicide is increasing but society has responsibility to help the people for getting rid from the tendency of various forms of suicide. Durkheim quoted "according to Esquirol 'Suicide shows all the characteristics of mental alienation.'— 'A man attempts self-destruction only in delirium and suicides are mentally alienated.'"²

Emile Durkheim identifies four different types of suicide: altruistic suicide, egoistic suicide, anomic suicide and fatalistic suicide. Altruistic suicide: When a person commits suicide avoiding of his own will controlled by society, family and others etc. is called altruistic suicide. In the case of altruistic suicide, man is always ready to give his life for the interest of others that could be country, family, society etc.

Egoistic suicide is seen as stemming from the absence of social integration. At this point, the ego-supreme person's thoughts are completely separate from the society's meditative ideas, so the human life is cut off from the society. In the case of the egoistic suicide, it is seen that a person with ego is always thinking of his own interests and he is isolated from the society due to his selfishness. As a result, he suffers from loneliness. In this condition many people commit suicide to get rid of the pain of loneliness. This is called egocentric suicide.

According to Durkheim "Egoistic suicide can be reduced by reintegrating the individual into group-life, giving him strong allegiances through a strengthened collective conscience. This can be accomplished in no small part, he thinks, through the re-establishment of occupational groups, compact voluntary associations based on work-interests..... The occupational group will also serve to limit the number of anomic suicides. In the case of conjugal anomy, his solution is in greater freedom and equality for women."³

Anomic suicide: A person who commits suicide in order to get rid of self-loathing or accusation is called anomic suicide. Many times, a person does something that degrades his self-esteem. He may commit suicide for fear of being scandal or Defamation in society by his crime and misdeed.

According to ultimate destinyists, there is no such thing as free and active human will, everything in human life happens according to destiny. There is deep despair in human life and when a person wants to get rid of this depression, he destroys his own life, it is called destiny suicide or fatalistic suicide.

Assisted suicide: Assisted suicide is the act of deliberately assisting another person to kill themselves. Here, it refers an action of a person who is intentionally assisting another person who is committing suicide. Cambridge Dictionary defined the assisted suicide as "the act of intentionally killing oneself with the assistance of another who deliberately provides the knowledge, means, or both".⁴ About assisted suicide Lisa Yount written 'in which a physician or, sometimes, a family member or friend provides the means for a person with a terminal or incurable illness to end life, but the patient is still the one who performs the final act'⁵.

What does mean by 'euthanasia'

The doctor's responsibility is to treat the patient as needed, not just to heal the sick patient. Because there are many patients who are suffering from an incurable disease i.e. there is no chance of them recovering from this disease, in this case the doctor has to see that patients can live painlessly as long as they live. That is, one of the main tasks of a physician is to alleviate the patient's pain. Euthanasia is a way through which the doctor can relieve the patient from pain. The terms 'euthanasia' is combined of two Greek words "Eu" and "Thanatos". 'Eu' means good and "Thanatos" mean death, euthanasia simply means 'good death' or 'gentle and easy death'. Euthanasia means gentle and easy death that benefits the person who dies. In the book 'The Cambridge Textbook of Bioethics' euthanasia has been defined as "a deliberate act undertaken by one person with the intention of ending the life of another person to relieve that person's suffering."⁶

Suppose an ill person is suffering with unbearable pain from incurable disease and also there is unavailable proper medical treatment, medicine or lifesaving treatment are very expensive for the patient. As there is no other way in medical science to relief the patient from pain except end his life. In this situation the patient or his parents may request to the doctor for helping him and to relief him from this enormous pain by giving the gentle and easy death. The doctor helps the patient to end his life either by injecting lethal medicine or by discontinuing lifesaving treatment, is called euthanasia. There are many essential aspects in euthanasia, such as it involves taking a human life, terminally illness, incurable disease or nonrecoverable injuries, suffering from a disease that is excruciatingly painful etc.

Y. V. Satyanarayana has written in his book ethics theory and practice 'Euthanasia is killing a terminally ill patient for the sake of mercy to relieve him from great suffering, or killing someone who is in an irreversible coma. Hastening the death of a terminally ill patient who is suffering from an incurable and painful disease, either by killing him with a Lethal Injection or by withdrawing medical procedures that prolong his life, is commonly known as Euthanasia or Mercy killing'⁷.

Different kinds of euthanasia

There are different types of euthanasia. It is necessary to distinguish between different types of euthanasia. One kind of difference is that the active and the passive euthanasia, which is determined by the mode of action of the person who helps the patient to die. This means that the doctor is doing something actively for ending patient's life. Suppose here a doctor injects poison into a patient's body with 'sedative hypnotics' for the purpose of patient's painless peaceful death. Y. V. Satyanarayana mention 'active Euthanasia means taking a direct action to kill the terminally ill patient giving him a lethal injection prescribed by the doctor'⁸

On the other hand, passive euthanasia is usually defined as withdrawing medical treatment with the intention to confirm patient's death peacefully. Here the doctors are not actively killing anyone, but not saving him. For example, if a patient requires oxygen for survive, and the doctors disconnect the oxygen mask or withdrawal the require treatment, resulted the patient will die soon. Lisa Yount mentioned passive euthanasia as 'ceasing or not starting medical treatment that keeps a person alive, such as attachment to a respirator or provision of food and water through a tube'⁹. There is another type of difference of euthanasia which is divided into three types based on the patient's consent. These are voluntary, involuntary and non-voluntary euthanasia.

Voluntary euthanasia: The first and the main condition of voluntary euthanasia is suffering with intolerable dieses with incurable pain or non-recoverable injury. The patient known well about his painful disease. And he is concerned about his death. Sometimes the decision of patient and his family not be same, in this case they may solve together with the discussion, but generally the patient's desire is finalized. The patient will give his concern by written or verbally but it must be very clear and meaningful. In the voluntary euthanasia believe that patient has freedom and he takes decision himself. With the respect of patient's permission voluntary euthanasia is done.

According to Y. V. Satyanarayana 'voluntary Euthanasia is Mercy killing of a terminally ill patient with his or her consent'¹⁰. For example, if a patient is suffering with intolerable pain due to an incurable disease or non-recoverable injury, he will have to suffer for as long as he lives, in this situation doctor kills the patient with his concern by fatal injection of morphine for reliving him or her from this painful life. In the case of voluntary Euthanasia patient want to die and make a request to effect it, decision-making capacity and he should express his wishes to family members or friends or doctors. Some countries allow voluntary Euthanasia in legally e.g., Luxembourg, Netherlands, Switzerland, Belgium etc.

Involuntary euthanasia: In the case of involuntary euthanasia, we see that the patient is suffering from an incurable disease with constant excruciating pain, and is unlikely to recover from the disease, but suffer will be continued as long as he or she survives. Sometimes the required treatment is also very costly. In this situation, doctor can talk to the family members and decide to end patient's life to relive him from pain. Though patient is not giving permission to end his life and he expressed desire for living, but the doctor to do something for ending patient's life then it is called involuntary euthanasia. Involuntary euthanasia is performed on a person who is able to provide informed consent, but does not, either because they do not want to die or not informed. Patient does not want to die; he is compulsorily killed. In the book *The Encyclopaedia of Libertarianism* mentioned 'involuntary Euthanasia is the Killing of someone against their will to help them escaped some inevitable ill fate'¹¹.

Non-voluntary euthanasia: The patient is not in a position to take any decisions about his life and he is not conscious the value of his life and the idea of death. In this stage patient do not have the mental ability to request euthanasia (such as Coma patient, infants, mad person). Here family member would take the decision of euthanasia for patient. They have responsibility for caring their family members. As the patient is suffering with incurable disease or not able to enjoy his life in this situation so, it is better for him to end his life peacefully. In some cases, we see where infants are typically born with a debilitating disease and so they are not able to live with a normal life. They may have brain damage; parts of body may not have fully formed. So, they are suffering with enormous pain. In these cases, it is better to end the lives of such infants ending life of a person who is in coma and cannot make a decision on his behalf. According to *The Encyclopaedia of Libertarianism* 'nonvoluntary euthanasia killing someone who is incapable of giving consent to help them escape some inevitable ill fate'¹². Sometimes involuntary and nonvoluntary euthanasia called mercy killing.

Some conflicts on euthanasia: There is disagreement over whether euthanasia is morally acceptable. Conservationists do not accept euthanasia as morally right, they argued that euthanasia is a violation of the natural laws and the commandments of God. Only God has the right to decide life and death, and in principle no other human being can make that decision. And when terminally ill innocent people are killed in the name of euthanasia, really a morally abominable act. They claim that human life is invaluable. Human's life cannot be taken away in exchange for anything. Euthanasia is nothing but a kind of murder. Some ethicist claim euthanasia is inhumane and if we make euthanasia legal then it can be applied to undesirable people. It can be misused and killed people, especially where euthanasia is decided without the patient's permission. Even some times the disease that was identified as incurable due to misdiagnosis by a doctor, is cured. Therefore, euthanasia cannot be supported from logical and moral point of view.

According to liberals, euthanasia is morally acceptable. The reason is that through euthanasia, patients suffering from incurable diseases are relieved of their pain by a painless peaceful death. Liberals argued "it is cruel and inhuman to refuse the plea of a terminally ill patient that his or her life be mercifully and peacefully ended it to avoid further suffering and dignity"¹³.

There are many incurable patients who suffer from unbearable physical pain as well as mental. They will have to suffer for as long as they live. They can get rid of this pain with the help of euthanasia. Also, many times the pain of death is so prolonged that it is very difficult to bear, in all these cases the death of the patient is morally desirable. We have responsibility to respect the person who is suffering from incurable disease and we should consider him accordingly his request. The patient is completely independent,

he can decide what will happen to his life. He can plea for a painless death and it is our moral responsibility to respond to that plea and give him a peaceful death.

Some complex issues in euthanasia:After discussing the different types of euthanasia, reviewing the various arguments for and against, some specific issues are raised. The moral future of Euthanasia depends on solving these issues.

Though euthanasia is different from murder but how can say it morally justified? Is a death or killing desirable?

When a desire of patient's death is helping to fulfil the patients and his family's interest then it is morally desirable otherwise not. In the other word when a death of the patient is bearing suffer or painful life to the patient's family then it not to be morally desirable.

When a desire of a person is morally valuable?

When a desire of a person brings good to his own and his family then it will be morally good and valuable. Person's desire always depends on the situations. Sometimes an individual's desire does not bring happiness to all. The desire of own death brings sadness to the relatives. So, euthanasia is not desirable always but, the euthanasia is desirable in some cases, where a terminally ill patient is living painful life.

Conditions of euthanasia:Now we will try to find out the main reasons of the euthanasia. Firstly, it may apply only in the case of physical illness and non-recoverable injuries; secondly the patient is suffering with unbearable pain by the incurable disease according to medical science. So, we may decide mainly these conditions are reliable to the euthanasia. It is difficult to define that when a pain is unbearable for a patient. Pain is varying to the subject. Anyway, when a patient repeating his/her concern in favour of euthanasia that is the only way to relief him from the pain, it may call unbearable pain. Sometimes a situation is arisen where the relatives of the patient think the pain is bearable but patient feels it is unbearable pain then patient's opinion should be given priority.

Secondly, pain is two different types—mental and physical pain. As there is available mental treatment in psychology and medical science for relieving mental pain, so euthanasia applicable to the patients who are suffering with physically intolerable pain by incurable disease. But when a disease may call incurable? If the treatment or medicine of disease unavailable according to medical science, then it may call incurable disease. For example, the final stage of cancer. There is no proper treatment to cure the patient from final stage of cancer. In this cases euthanasia may applicable. Another controversial issue arises in some situations where the medical treatments or medicines are very expensive, patient or his family aren't able to bear the cost of the treatments, in this situation euthanasia is considerable.

Sometimes it may be accused that the active euthanasia is an act of murder, as in the case of the active euthanasia a doctor inject poison and sleeping drug into patient's body for killing purpose. It is clear that the euthanasia is different from murder. If a terminally ill patient is given peaceful easy and gentle death is called euthanasia. In the case of euthanasia, the patient's interests are taken into account in order to relieve him from intolerable pain, so that his death may be peaceful. Here, doctor kill the patient in favour of patient's interest, he is not killing the patient for fulfilling his purpose. On the other hand, in the case of murder; only murderer fulfil satisfaction themselves through killings others.

According to utilitarian view an action is right when its end is good, and an action is wrong when its end is bad. Even according to deontological theory, we cannot use a person as a means to an end. Every person in the society has intrinsic value. Which doesn't depend on other. Patient not to be used as means or instrument for other purpose. We have to admit intrinsic value of the patient instead of instrumental value. Therefore, we can say active euthanasia and passive euthanasia both are morally wrong. Ms. McManus said "Euthanasia is something you do to a horse, or to an animal. When you do it to people, it's called murder."¹⁴

However, some ethicist believe that euthanasia is not an act of murder, when a patient is suffering with terrible pain the euthanasia saves and relive him from this painful life. So, it is such a sympathy and love. Paul Heslin argues "euthanasia is humane and compassionate when applied to the right situations"¹⁵. In the case of euthanasia, it can be said that the patient is not being used as a means to an end, but the patient's painless death is the purpose here. Again, what does it mean to be good? Good means increasing happiness and decreasing sadness, bad means decreasing happiness and increasing sadness in human's life. As euthanasia produce good things (as increasing happiness and relieving sadness to the patient and his family) so it is morally right.

We have responsibility to help the patient for realizing his good and meaningful life, where he is not able to decide good one himself. At this stage doctors disconnect life sustaining necessary treatments of physically ill patient and help him to die peacefully. Here a question arises why we apply euthanasia to the Coma patient who is not suffering pain? The answer is a Coma patient has no control over his own body and mind, no real possibility of recovery from his present situation, he has no competent to take decision,

even he has no cognitive capacity and he is not enjoying his life. So, there is no difference between him and an object. This stage of his life is not valuable. Therefore, it will be morally good if we help him to die peacefully.

If the euthanasia is legalized, we can never deny the possibility that the euthanasia could be misused that could lead to the killing of innocent people. However, if the euthanasia is legalized, its security will be much higher. Legal euthanasia helps to people's safety. If we make euthanasia legal then the standard of euthanasia, its practice, protocol everything will be develop. Resulted illegally force for euthanasia can be prevented. Even it is also very complicated to select a patient's euthanasia based on his unbearable pain. Because there is no valid or legal way in medical science for knowing whether the patient is really feeling unbearable pain or not. We may use the lie detector method (Polygraph Test) to find out right information about patient's pain. Today it is important to consider whether the use of lie detector methods can be considered legal. With the help of advanced technology, if we get true information about the patient's suffering, then medical science can be further strengthened and the society can be formed as an orderly and healthy society. Although this lie detector method has some limitations, but it is able to give a lot of true information. Under the Right to Information Act, 2005 (India), we collect a lot of information that we did not get in the past. In many cases, information had not made in public due to privacy concerns. But today different information in all those fields is presented to the people through the RTI. Therefore, it is important to give legal permission to use all the necessary technology in people's interest of the society. Although we have to try to find a solution to all the problems by obeying the rules and regulations.

Conclusion

The debate surrounding euthanasia is never far from the headlines, particularly while its legal and moral status remains inadequate and discursive. In many cases the decision of euthanasia puts us in a confusing situation and raises many problems in our lives. Therefore, the overall situation and the patient's own decision is the most important and relevant in the application of euthanasia. The decision of euthanasia should apply after judging these issues. However, in case of euthanasia, death should be allowed on the basis of the patient's utility. We have to decide the euthanasia only by trusting in the words of the patient. It should be strict that without his permission euthanasia not to be allowed. Adequate rules, protections, certain conditions, etc. need to be strengthened. Care must be taken to ensure that the death does not apply illegally. Euthanasia is a desirable subject on the basis of its usefulness in the society. This is our responsibility to a terminally ill patient, who may die a dignified death in his or her last life that is what people deserve.

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